

Studies on Repeptisation of Coagulated Flocculi

S. Bandyopadhyay

Coagulation is generally considered to be an irreversible process. Coagulated flocculi of thorium hydroxide sol can be easily repeptised merely by diluting the system with water in 1:1 ratio. The sol undergoing coagulation, both at slow and rapid rates in the presence of uni- and polyvalent counter ions, can be repeptised, the degree of repeptisation diminishing with the increase in valency of the counter ions. The repeptisation study has been followed spectrophotometrically and S-shaped curves have been obtained. As_2S_3 sol shows no repeptisation.

The question, how far coagulation is reversible, has attracted the attention of many early investigators in colloid science. It has been observed that precipitates of some oxides begin to be peptised when repeatedly washed with distilled water (e.g., V_2O_5 sol¹). In some cases, washing the precipitate is not enough and addition of small quantities of a suitable electrolyte is necessary (e.g., AgI sol²) for peptisation.

Flocculated hydroxide sols are remarkable for the ease with which these can be peptised. In this connection, experiments performed by Linder and Picton³ on Fe_2O_3 sol and those by Freundlich and Leonhardt⁴ on V_2O_5 and Mo_2O_5 sols are noteworthy. Factors, which should be considered for redispersion, are the interval between flocculation and repeptisation, valency of the coagulating ions, adsorbability of the peptising ions, the temperature, the presence of non-electrolyte, hydration of the sol, etc.

In all earlier works, some of which have been cited above, it was necessary to take recourse to somewhat drastic steps such as continued washing, followed sometimes by the addition of a little peptising agent, and vigorous shaking. It is worth investigating whether operations, which are less drastic in nature, can lead to any repeptisation. As earlier references, we may cite the experiments on congorubin, V_2O_5 , and benzopurpurin sols^{5,6}.

In this communication some fresh work on the redispersion of ThO_2 sol at different stages of coagulation (both slow and rapid) by electrolytes has been recorded.

Theoretical Considerations due to Hamaker⁷

In order to visualise a complete picture of the colloidal behaviour, apart from the double-layer repulsion and the London-Van der Waals attraction, yet another sort of forces, viz., the short range Born repulsion, has to be considered but for which, the mini-

1. Blitz, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 1098.
2. Kruyt and Klompe, *Kolloid Beihefte*, 1943, 54, 507.
3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 67, 1926.
4. *Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1915, 7, 179.
5. Ostwald, *ibid.*, 1919, 10, 226.
6. Zocher, *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1921, 98, 319.
7. Hamaker, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1937, 56, 3.

imum with a finite value in the potential-energy curve would have been replaced by an infinitely large negative value of the potential energy in a flocculated system and repeptisation would have been impossible. By removing the flocculating electrolyte, the double-layer repulsion may become great enough to cause this finite minimum to disappear completely so that spontaneous repeptisation may follow.

An application of this line of thought is still lacking. Redispersal after coagulation is an interesting phenomenon that might provide information on the innermost parts of the double layer (vide Kruyt⁸).

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of the Sol and its Characteristics.—Thorium oxide sol was prepared by Müller's method⁸ with a slight modification. The positively charged, almost transparent colloid had ThO₂ concentration of 2.5% by weight and pH 3.54. Its specific conductance at 25° was 1.27×10^{-4} mho cm⁻¹. The sol was selected for study because of its very small absorption of light in the visible range of the spectrum.

Procedure.—The sol was allowed to coagulate to the desired extent (characterised by the percentage transmission I_t^m of the sol-electrolyte mixture with respect to distilled water) by mixing it with electrolytes like KNO₃, K₂SO₄, and K-citrate of such concentrations as to cause rapid and slow rates of coagulation. When the desired extent was reached, the sol-electrolyte mixture was diluted with distilled water in the ratio 1:1 and the percentage transmission I_t of the resulting system was measured immediately and at regular intervals of time t at $\lambda = 540$ m μ in a Beckman spectrophotometer (model DU). The time of dilution has been reckoned as zero time.

Percentage transmission at $\lambda = 540$ m μ of the doubly diluted ThO₂ sol is 98.5. Experiments were carried at a constant temperature of 25°. The data are represented by curves 1-10 (Figs. 1-4) and the interval of time after which the colloid-electrolyte mixture is diluted has also been noted in the illustration of figures.

Illustration of figures.

In curve 1	Time of dilution = 70 mins.	corresponding to	$C_{KNO_3} = 62.5$ mM/l	and $I_t^m = 19$
2	" = 120 "	" "	" = 500 "	" = 49.5
3	" = 22 hours	" "	" = 41.7 "	" = 51.5
4	" = 50 mins.	" "	" = 76.2 "	" = 7.6
5	" = 60 "	" "	$C_{K_2SO_4} = 1.67$ "	" = 77.9
6	" = 60 "	" "	" = 2.00 "	" = 42.6
7	" = 75 "	" "	" = 2.50 "	" = 10.0
8	" = 33 "	" "	$C_{K-cit} = 1.00$ "	" = 65.5
9	" = 70 "	" "	" = 1.25 "	" = 47.5
10	" = 60 "	" "	" = 1.67 "	" = 5.8

8. Müller, *Ber.*, 1903, **35**, 4436.

9. "Colloid Science", p. 334.

DISCUSSION

The gradual disintegration of the coagulum on dilution with an equal volume of distilled water is indicated by the increase in percentage transmission of the system. It appears from Figs. 1-5 that ThO_2 sol, partially coagulated with counter ions of different valencies, can be reprecipitated merely by diluting the system with water in the ratio of 1:1 even when coagulation has proceeded to a considerable extent. In an actual experiment (not recorded in the figures) a ThO_2 flocculus completely precipitated by nitrate ions has been found to attain the state of complete reprecipitation in 24 hours, merely on dilution.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

When univalent counter ions are used as coagulant, nearly complete reprecipitation of the system occurs; reprecipitated mass after 24 hours or so attains a constant state corresponding to about 95.5% transmission in all cases. This value is very near to that of the original doubly diluted ThO_2 sol. The sol undergoing coagulation at a rapid rate can also be reprecipitated. The extent of redispersion, however, decreases as the valency of the counter ions increases.

FIG. 3

FIG. 4

Along with the progress of repeptisation, a slight precipitation of the sol also occurs when polyvalent counter ions (especially citrate ions) are used. This phenomenon has not been observed with univalent counter ions. When polyvalent counter ions are used as coagulants, repeptisation continues even 24 hours after dilution.

FIG. 5

The ageing of a flocculus has an influence on the rate of reptisation. Thus a system diluted 22 hours after the addition of electrolyte (vide curve 3) reptises more slowly than that diluted at an early stage of coagulation (vide curve 1), although the concentration of electrolyte in the former case is lower than that in the latter one.

A typical hydrophobic colloid, viz, As_2S_3 sol, has also been studied in a similar manner at $\lambda=580$ m μ . but no reptisation has been noticed. On the other hand, coagulation still continues even after dilution of the system. When the dilution is made with water containing H_2S , a slight tendency of redispersion can be noticed by a slight increase in the percentage transmission after a considerable length of time. With ammonium polysulphide, however, as the phenomenon is well known, specially in a fairly concentrated solution, appreciable reptisation occurs.

Reptisation curves have been found to be S-shaped; the higher the valency of the coagulating ions, the more prominent is the S-shape. It is also pronounced where the rate of coagulation is rapid.

The flocculation value of an electrolyte is determined mainly by the height of the maximum of the potential-energy curve above the axis. For reptisation, the vertical distance of separation between the maximum and the minimum of the potential-energy diagram has to be smaller than several times kT . Ordinarily, the reptisation state is reached for a very much higher repulsion than the flocculation state. Thus electrolyte concentration must be greatly reduced. The large difference between the flocculating and reptisation concentration is thus understandable. In this experiment with ThO_2 sol, this difference, however, should be small, as is evident from the ease with which redispersion can be brought about. Further works in this line are in progress.

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